

STRENGTH AND FATIGUE LIFE OF CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES UNDER BIAXIAL LOADING

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SUMMARY: The static and fatigue tests of cross-ply carbon/epoxy composite tubes were performed under combined axial and torsional loading up to failure. Strength properties were evaluated as a function of biaxial ratio. The fatigue life predictions previously proposed have been modified in the use of reference modulus concept and stress function. Using the cumulative damage concept, fatigue life prediction on composite laminates has been made for biaxial stress condition as well as uniaxial stress condition. It was shown that the proposed theory has wide applicability as well as has good agreement with experimental data.

KEYWORDS: carbon-matrix composites, biaxial loading, damage, fatigue life prediction, strength, fatigue modulus

INTRODUCTION

The majority of components and structures in service are subjected to multi-axial loading conditions, resulting in biaxial and triaxial states of stress. Pressure vessels, turbine blades, crank shafts and aircraft structures are all common examples. Failure mechanisms of FRP are more complex under multi-axial loading than under uniaxial loading. Evaluation of FRP under multi-axial loading, thus, is important for designing composite structures. Moreover, fatigue analysis has been required as one of the essential procedures to determine a service life for reliable design of the structures. Development of analytical method for the prediction of fatigue life in terms of fatigue load and fatigue cycles is needed for general laminates under multi-axial loading.

Under uniaxial loading, some theories for fatigue life prediction of FRP have been proposed at constant amplitude stress condition [1-6] and at two-stress level [7-9]. A damage variable using modulus degradation rate has been successfully applied [6-8]. Fawaz and Ellyin [10] proposed a new model which predicts the fatigue failure of FRP under multi-axial stresses, varying minimum to maximum cyclic stress ratios and different fiber orientations with respect to the loading directions by introducing the concept of elementary blocks. However, it may be difficult to apply his model to multi-directional composite laminates. Recently Fawaz [11] presents a phenomenological model for predicting the multi-axial fatigue failure of FRP using a tensor polynomial formulation. Until now, there is no theory considering material non-linearity for fatigue life prediction of composite materials subjected to biaxial loads.

In this study, fatigue modulus was used for stiffness parameter. The fatigue life prediction previously proposed has been modified in the use of reference modulus concept and new stress function for the life prediction of composite laminates under multi-axial fatigue loading.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Fatigue Modulus Concept

The stress-strain curve of composite materials under cyclic loading changes due to degradation as shown in Fig. 1. Fatigue modulus F is a slope of a line on', while E and S denote elastic modulus and secant modulus, respectively. Therefore,

$$F(n, q) = \frac{\sigma_a}{\varepsilon(n)} = \sigma_u \frac{q}{\varepsilon(n)} \quad (1)$$

where $F(n, q)$ is the fatigue modulus at n th loading cycle under applied stress level q , $\varepsilon(n)$ is the resultant strain at n th loading cycle, and q is the ratio of applied stress σ_a to ultimate strength σ_u .

Fig.1: Fatigue modulus concept

Fig. 2: Initial fatigue modulus for matrix dominated composites

The fatigue modulus F of a material is a function of loading cycle n and applied stress level q . For the fiber dominated composite laminates, the stress/strain relation is almost linear up to failure. Hence, fatigue modulus at the 0th cycle F_0 is assumed to be the same as elastic modulus E_0 , and fatigue modulus at fracture is defined as F_f at the number of cycles to failure N . F_0 should be constant regardless of applied stress, whereas F_f depends on applied stress. However matrix dominated laminates such as cross-ply CFRP under torsional loading shows a material nonlinearity. Thus above assumptions are not applicable and a new approach be expected. For a material having nonlinear stress/strain relation, initial fatigue modulus depends on the applied stress level as shown in Fig. 2. The relation of initial fatigue modulus and elastic modulus was suggested by Yang et al. [5] and can be written, using the relation of $\sigma_a = \sigma_u q$, as

$$F_0 = G(q)E_0 \quad (2.a)$$

$$\text{where } G(q) = \sigma_u q / \xi \ln\{\xi / (\xi - \sigma_u q)\} \quad (2.b)$$

In Eqn (2.b), ξ is the material constant having as same dimension as stress, obtained from static test [12].

Fatigue Life Prediction

The fatigue modulus degradation rate at any fatigue cycle can be assumed as a power function of number of fatigue cycles,

$$dF(n, q)/dn = -F_0 a C n^{C-1} \quad (3)$$

where a and C are material constants. From Eqn 3 one obtains [12]

$$N = H [p + Z^{-1} \ln(1 - Zq)]^J \quad (4.a)$$

$$\text{where } Z = \sigma_u / \xi \quad (4.b)$$

In Eqn 4, p and q are material constant and applied stress level, respectively. And $H(= (pa)^{-1/C})$ and $J(=1/C)$ are material properties. Z can be determined from static test while p , H and J can be determined from fatigue data. Dimensionless number Z can indicate stress-strain property of a material whether the material is linear or nonlinear. Z approach zero for the fiber dominated composites, while Z can get near unity for the matrix dominated composites [13].

Fatigue damage of a material depends on number of fatigue cycles n , applied stress level q , frequency f , temperature T , moisture content M , geometric shape of the specimen, *etc.* As a first approach, constant environmental conditions are assumed. In addition, the effect of frequency and temperature rise during a fatigue test is ignored. There are many indicators to describe the degree of internal damage state of composite materials. For example, number of cracks, crack length, delaminated area, residual stiffness, residual strength and residual strain can be used such indicators. Among them, modulus is often chosen as an indicator for the damage variable D , which is defined, in this study, using fatigue modulus and resultant strain as follows.

$$D = \frac{\varepsilon(n, \sigma_a) - \varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon_f - \varepsilon_0} = \frac{F_f}{F(n, \sigma_a)} \frac{F_0 - F(n, \sigma_a)}{F_0 - F_f} \quad (5)$$

where D is the damage variable under corresponding stress σ_a . The cumulative damage models can be derived as functions of applied stress level q , number of fatigue cycles n , and material constants:

$$D = g(n)h(q) \quad (6.a)$$

$$\text{where, } g(n) = an^c / (1 - an^c) \quad (6.b)$$

$$h(q) = -\ln(1 - Zq) / \{pZ + \ln(1 - Zq)\} \quad (6.c)$$

In Eqn 6, p , a and c are calculated from corresponding fatigue loading. $g(n)$ describes the effect of fatigue cycles on fatigue damage, while $h(q)$ is function of applied stress level including static properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

An MTS 809 Axial-Torsional Test System was used for static and fatigue testing. The specimen was bi-directional (cross-ply) carbon fiber-epoxy tube made by the lapped molding technique because the tubular specimen is the first choice for a biaxial test of FRP because of its relevance to practical situations in engineering applications. In the lapped molding

technique, prepregs are laminated with an overlap, rolled around inner mold and lapped with heat-shrinkage film. At last, the closed mold is cured in an oven with $135\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After curing, the tubes were cut into 100 mm lengths and glass cloth end-tabs 35 mm long with 30 mm outside diameter were attached to the outside of the tube. The specimens have a inner diameter of 20 mm, a wall thickness of 0.65 to 0.7 mm and a gage length of 50 mm. The volume fraction of fibers was about 58 %. The grips and the end reinforcement were designed to minimize stress concentrations in the test section. Aluminum liners were inserted into the inside of the specimen ends.

In static test, eleven biaxial ratios were used: $R_b = \infty$ (uniaxial tension), 20, 10, 5, 2, 1, 0 (pure torsion), -2, -5, -10, $-\infty$ (uniaxial compression). Typically five specimens were tested for each biaxial ratio. To determine baseline of effects of compression on biaxial strength, two specimens were tested in combined compression and torsion. The tensile-tensile fatigue tests were carried out at five biaxial ratios ($R_b = \infty, 10, 5, 2, 0$) under load and torque controlled mode with sinusoidal load wave form. The stress ratio in fatigue was $R = 0.05$. Fig. 3 shows static and fatigue loading conditions and deformation configuration. The frequency was 0.25 Hz which is believed to give a negligible temperature rise during test. Fatigue tests were conducted at five stress levels: 0.8, 0.75, 0.7, 0.65 and 0.6 of the ultimate tensile strength. During fatigue tests, the load and the strain level were monitored from the signal of the load cell. The tests were conducted at room temperature under laboratory conditions.

Fig. 3: Loading and deformation configuration [14]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 4 shows the biaxial strength data according to biaxial ratio. The slight increase of the shear strength with increased axial tension in lower biaxial ratios occurs due to the presence of axial fibers. At higher biaxial ratios, significant decrease in shear strength with superposed tension across the shear plane occurs due to the change of failure mode from matrix shear mode to fiber failure mode. Average maximum strength and modulus were found to be 724 MPa and 34 GPa for tension, and 88 MPa and 2.8 GPa for torsion. In the figure, solid line presents the failure surface predicted by artificial neural network [14].

Fig. 4: Biaxial strength depending on failure mode

Some extreme scattering cases were observed at fatigue tests. The slope of S-N curve decrease with increasing biaxial ratio. Uniaxial fatigue life predictions and experimental data are compared in Fig. 5. In the figure, further prediction made by S-N relation is also shown. Conventional S-N curve can be written as follows:

$$q = k \log(N) + d \quad (7)$$

where k and d are material constants.

To compare the accuracy of prediction equations, the RMS (root mean square) error could be defined as follows.

$$E_{rms} = \frac{1}{m} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (\log N_{exp} - \log N_{cal})^2} \quad (8)$$

where N_{exp} is the experimental data, N_{cal} is the fatigue life predicted by life equations, and m is the number of data. The RMS error gives a brief overall comparison, although the RMS error alone cannot settle the superiority of prediction models. The constants in Eqn 4 and Eqn 7 are estimated by the least squares methods using the SAS program. The results are presented in Table 1. The results show that the proposed equation predict fatigue life very well for this material system.

The prediction of fatigue life under multi-axial loading is compared with experimental data in Fig. 6. The comparison shows reasonable correlation with the experimental data, though there exist some errors at low biaxial ratio.

Table 1: Estimation of material constants

Equations	Constants	Values	
		Tension	Torsion
Proposed	ξ	1901.3000	93.3480
	p	2.1999	1.9869
	H	7.7000	3.7377
	J	43.4999	5.3468
	a	0.4337	0.3933
	C	0.0230	0.1870
	E_{rms}	0.0298	0.0556
S-N curve	k	-0.0497	-0.1046
	d	1.0503	0.9656
	E_{rms}	0.0267	0.0841

Fig. 5: Comparison of predictions with experimental data at uniaxial fatigue loading

Fig. 6: Comparison of prediction with experimental data at multi-axial fatigue loading

CONCLUSIONS

There is a strong interaction between the axial stress and the shear stress at failure. The equation developed based on the reference modulus concept and a stress function could predict fatigue life of composite materials, involving matrix dominant as well as fiber dominated behavior, as a function of applied stress level. To predict fatigue life at multi-axial loading, cumulative damage model was derived as functions of applied stress level and number of fatigue cycle. It was shown that the proposed equation are more practical in fatigue life prediction of composite materials due to flexibility of curve and the prediction agrees well with experimental data.

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